

Student Leadership Development Programs: An Evaluation of the Office of Student Affairs' Initiatives at San Isidro College

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ABSTRACT

Strong leadership among students enriches the academic community, driving effective governance, and fostering growth within organizations. Programs that build leadership competencies play a vital role in ensuring the success of these initiatives and preparing students for future leadership opportunities. This study examines the effectiveness of the student leadership development programs implemented by the Office of Student Affairs at San Isidro College. Student leaders from various organizations participated in a program aimed at enhancing their leadership skills, with assessments conducted before and after the training. The study indicated that the leadership training program enhanced various leadership competencies among student leaders to a degree. These findings underscore the program's capacity to foster well-rounded leadership development and identify areas for further refinement to maximize its impact. Although the results demonstrated some improvement, the overall outcome revealed that the student leaders' leadership skills remained at a low-level. The recommendations emphasize a comprehensive redesign of the leadership training program, incorporating tailored content, experiential learning, continuous evaluation, and skill-specific strategies to address and improve low-level leadership competencies.

Keywords: *Student Leadership, Leadership Training, Office of Student Affairs and Services, Leadership Skills, Student Development Program*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Student leadership plays a pivotal role in nurturing a vibrant and dynamic academic environment, empowering individuals to contribute meaningfully to their institutions and communities. Student leaders often act as the voice of their peers, facilitating communication between the administration and the student body while championing initiatives that promote

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inclusivity and growth (Dedicatoria et al., 2023). The development of leadership skills is essential for ensuring the effective functioning of student organizations, as these entities rely on competent, motivated leaders to plan, organize, and execute activities that enhance campus life (Castro et al., 2020). Cultivating these skills not only enriches the student experience but also prepares individuals for leadership roles beyond the academic setting (Paraiso, 2021).

Despite student leadership's evident importance, there is a lack of empirical research evaluating the effectiveness of leadership training programs within higher education institutions (Schweisfurth et al., 2018). While numerous programs exist to enhance leadership capabilities, their impact on student leaders' competence and organizational efficiency remains underexplored (Amit, 2019; Friaes, 2021). This gap underscores the necessity for systematic evaluation to ensure that these programs are equipping students with the skills and knowledge required to thrive as leaders. Addressing this gap is critical to refining existing initiatives and developing evidence-based strategies that foster sustainable leadership development.

CMO No. 09, s. 2013 underscores the need to prioritize leadership development. This directive emphasizes the importance of enhancing student services and policies to cultivate well-rounded individuals. This directive highlights the responsibility of educational institutions to provide structured, outcome-driven programs that align with national standards. By evaluating the leadership initiatives of the Office of Student Affairs, this study aligns with these enhanced guidelines, contributing to the broader goal of improving student affairs and fostering leadership excellence in higher education (Beltran, 2019b; Loyola, 2022).

This study aims to evaluate the student leadership training program implemented by the Office of Student Affairs to determine its effectiveness in developing essential leadership competencies among student leaders.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the principles of Transformational Leadership Theory (Siangchokyoo et al., 2020), which emphasizes inspiring and motivating student leaders to achieve their full potential while fostering a shared vision and collective purpose. This theory aligns closely with the goals of student leadership development programs, as it provides a framework for nurturing leaders who can inspire peers, drive meaningful change, and build collaborative environments within their organizations. Furthermore, the theory is further underscored by CMO No. 9, s. 2013, which highlights the importance of holistic student development and leadership in student affairs. Anchoring the study on this theory provides a strong foundation for evaluating how leadership training initiatives empower students to meet these expectations effectively.

Figure 1.
Schematic diagram of the study.

The schematic diagram of the study illustrates a systematic process that begins with an initial evaluation of the student leadership skills of participants to establish a baseline. This assessment

identifies the current competencies and areas for improvement among student leaders. Following this, the student leadership training program is implemented, designed to address the gaps and enhance key leadership skills through targeted activities and interventions. After the completion of the training program, a reassessment is conducted to measure the development and improvement in the participants' leadership abilities. This process allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the program's effectiveness, highlighting its effect on fostering essential leadership competencies and aligning with the goals of student organizations.

Statement of the Problem

The study seeks to explore how the initiatives of the Office of Student Affairs contribute to the holistic development of student leaders while supporting the efficient operation of student organizations. Through this evaluation, the study provides actionable insights to enhance program outcomes and align them with the leadership demands of the academic community. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following:

1. Is there a significant improvement on the student leadership skills of the student leaders before and after the student leadership training program of the Office of Student Affairs?
2. Is there a significant difference between the student leadership skills of the student leaders regarding the student leadership training program of the Office of Student Affairs considering:
 - a. pre-implementation of the training program; and
 - b. post-implementation of the training program?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a pre-experimental design (Jimenez-Buedo, 2018) to evaluate the effect of the student leadership training program. This design involved measuring the participants' leadership skills before and after the program's implementation to assess its effectiveness. Since all student leaders were included in the study, the focus was on observing changes within the same group of participants over time.

Sampling Technique

The study was conducted at San Isidro College and involved student leaders from various curricular and co-curricular organizations under the Office of Student Affairs. Initially, as presented in Table 1, sixty-six (66) student leaders were determined as respondents; however, by the conclusion of the training program, ninety-nine (99) student leaders had participated. These respondents not only underwent the leadership training program but also provided feedback to evaluate its effectiveness, ensuring comprehensive representation across the organizations.

Table 1.
Demographic profile of the student leaders.

Demographic	Pre-Implementation (N=66)		Post-Implementation (N=99)		
	F	%	F	%	
Sex	Male	21	21.2	33	33.3
	Female	45	45.5	66	66.7
Year	First	1	1.0	3	3.0
	Second	30	30.3	38	38.4
	Third	21	21.2	35	35.4
	Fourth	14	14.1	23	23.2
Course	AB	5	5.1	8	8.1
	BEEd	3	3.0	6	6.1
	BSEd	13	13.1	14	14.1
	BSA	6	6.1	18	18.2
	BSBA	11	11.1	14	14.1
	BSCE	6	6.1	5	5.1
	BSIT	3	3.0	12	12.1
	BSN	19	19.2	19	19.2
	BSOA	0	0.0	3	3.00

A total population sampling method (Lohr, 2021) was employed, including all student leaders affiliated with the Office of Student Affairs as respondents. This sampling method ensured that every leader had the opportunity to participate, reflecting the institution's collective leadership landscape. By involving the entire population of student leaders, the study captured a holistic view of the program's impact and ensured that the findings were representative of the leadership training's overall effectiveness.

Research Process

The study employed a research-developed questionnaire as the primary data collection tool to evaluate the leadership skills of student leaders. Experts in the field rigorously validated this instrument to ensure its relevance and reliability, followed by a pilot test that yielded a high Cronbach's alpha value of 0.957, indicating excellent internal consistency. The questionnaire was designed to capture various dimensions of leadership skills and was administered to student leaders before and after the implementation of the training program. The survey method facilitated efficient data collection from the participants, ensuring a systematic approach to gathering insights about the effectiveness of the program.

The leadership training program featured a combination of expert-led sessions and interactive activities designed to engage participants and enhance their leadership competencies. Experienced speakers, including professionals and educators with expertise in leadership development, delivered talks and workshops on topics. These sessions were complemented by hands-on activities that allowed student leaders to apply theoretical concepts in practical scenarios, fostering a deeper understanding of leadership principles. The integration of lectures and experiential exercises ensured a dynamic and comprehensive training approach, encouraging active participation and skill development among the student leaders.

The training was conducted over a two-month period during the designated student activity days to prevent conflicts with the academic schedules of the student leaders. The two-months leadership training program was conducted in accordance with ethical research standards, particularly with respect to data privacy and anonymity. Student leaders who participated in the survey were assured that their responses would remain confidential and would be used solely to evaluate the training program. This process ensured that participants could provide honest and accurate feedback.

Data Analysis

As presented in Table 2, the Shapiro-Wilk test was performed for the student leadership skills assessment pre-implementation ($W=0.948$, $p=0.088$) and post-implementation ($W=0.871$, $p=0.105$) and did not show evidence of non-normality. Based on the result presented in Table 2, the researchers opted to use parametric test.

Table 2.
Test for normality (Shapiro-Wilk)

Variable	W	p
Pre-Implementation	0.948	0.088
Post-Implementation	0.871	0.105

The study employed a combination of descriptive and inferential statistical methods to analyze the data collected. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and describe the student leaders' leadership skill levels, providing an overview of the data before and after the training program. To determine the effectiveness of the program in enhancing leadership skills, a paired t-test was conducted to compare the pre- and post-training scores, highlighting any significant improvements in overall leadership competence. Additionally, an ANOVA was utilized to examine variations in individual leadership skills among the participants, identifying which specific competencies demonstrated the most substantial development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Student Leadership Training Program

Communication Skill

Table 3 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison between the communication skills of the student leaders before and after the implementation of the student leadership training by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 3.
Comparison of the communication skills of the student leaders.

Conduct	N	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	t	p
Pre-Implementation	66	2.32	0.812	Low Level	-1.180	0.240
Post-Implementation	99	2.48	0.854	Low Level		

The comparison of communication skills, as presented in Table 3, before and after the implementation of the leadership training program revealed a slight increase in the mean score from 2.32 (± 0.812) to 2.48 (± 0.854). However, the computed t-value of -1.180 ($p=0.240$) indicates

that the observed difference is not statistically significant. While the program may have introduced elements aimed at improving communication skills, these findings suggest that the changes were not substantial enough to reach statistical significance, highlighting the need for a more targeted approach to enhancing this critical leadership competency.

The results underscore the importance of refining the training program to align more closely with the communication needs of student leaders. Effective communication is a foundational aspect of leadership, essential for motivating peers and fostering collaborative environments (Orbeta & Corpus, 2021). The slight improvement suggests potential but also indicates areas where the program could integrate more interactive and skill-specific activities to develop communication capabilities further (Gonzales, 2020). This finding emphasizes the need for training initiatives to not only inspire but also equip student leaders with practical tools to effectively convey ideas, resolve conflicts, and build trust within their organizations, fostering transformative leadership outcomes (Rogayan et al., 2021; Fernando & Bual, 2024).

Teamwork and Collaboration Skill

Table 4 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison between the teamwork and collaboration skills of the student leaders before and after the implementation of the student leadership training by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 4.
Comparison of the teamwork and collaboration skills of the student leaders.

Conduct	N	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	t	p
Pre-Implementation	66	2.07	0.912	Low Level	-1.375	0.172
Post-Implementation	99	2.30	1.136	Low Level		

The comparison of teamwork and collaboration skills, as presented in Table 4, before and after the training program revealed an increase in the mean score from 2.07 (± 0.912) to 2.30 (± 1.136). Despite this improvement, the t-value of -1.375 ($p=0.172$) suggests that the difference is not statistically significant. While the results indicate some enhancement in teamwork and collaboration, the lack of statistical significance implies that the changes may not be enough to confirm a substantial impact of the training program on this particular skill.

These findings highlight the need for a more deliberate focus on fostering teamwork and collaboration within the training program. As teamwork is a critical component of effective leadership, the program must prioritize activities and strategies that promote mutual respect, shared responsibilities, and collective problem-solving among student leaders (Bautista & Lim, 2021; Sarong, 2024). The observed improvements suggest a foundation to build, emphasizing the importance of creating an environment that inspires cooperation and equips student leaders with practical experiences to enhance their ability to lead teams effectively (Mugot & Sumbalan, 2019; Gonzales, 2020). Strengthening this aspect of the program could lead to more profound and lasting impacts on the participants' leadership capacities.

Problem-Solving and Decision-Making Skill

Table 5 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison between the problem-solving and decision-making skills of the student leaders before and after the implementation of the student leadership training by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 5.

Comparison of the problem-solving and decision-making skills of the student leaders.

Conduct	N	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	t	p
Pre-Implementation	66	2.20	0.832	Low Level	-1.114	0.267
Post-Implementation	99	2.36	0.954	Low Level		

The comparison of problem-solving and decision-making skills, as presented in Table 5, before and after the training program revealed an increase in the mean score from 2.20 (± 0.832) to 2.36 (± 0.954). Despite this improvement, the t-value of -1.114 ($p=0.267$) suggests that the difference is not statistically significant. While the findings suggest some improvement in these critical leadership skills, the change is not substantial enough to confirm a significant effect of the training program on enhancing problem-solving and decision-making abilities.

The findings underscore the need to strengthen the training program's focus on equipping student leaders with strategies for making effective decisions and solving problems in complex situations. These skills are essential for navigating challenges within their organizations and driving meaningful change (Gonzales, 2020). The observed improvement, though modest, suggests the program's potential to inspire growth, but it also emphasizes the need for more targeted interventions, such as scenario-based activities or case studies. Enhancing the program to provide student leaders with transformative experiences can better prepare them to address challenges proactively, align their decisions with organizational goals, and empower others to contribute to collective success (Kilag et al., 2023; Fernando & Bual, 2024).

Conflict Resolution Skill

Table 6 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison between the conflict resolution skills of the student leaders before and after the implementation of the student leadership training by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 6.

Comparison of the conflict resolution skills of the student leaders.

Conduct	N	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	t	p
Pre-Implementation	66	2.16	0.814	Low Level	-1.080	0.282
Post-Implementation	99	2.32	0.936	Low Level		

The comparison of conflict resolution skills, as presented in Table 6, before and after the training program indicated a slight increase in the mean score from 2.16 (± 0.814) to 2.32 (± 0.936). However, the t-value of -1.080 ($p=0.282$) shows this difference is not statistically significant. While the results suggest some improvement in the participants' ability to handle and resolve conflicts, the data does not provide enough evidence to conclude that the training program had a meaningful impact on this skill area.

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The modest improvement in conflict resolution skills highlights the program's potential to influence this critical aspect of leadership but also underscores the need for more focused and intensive approaches. Conflict resolution fosters harmony within student organizations and maintains productive group dynamics (Nyaga, 2018). Enhancing this training program component through practical applications could give student leaders the tools to address disputes effectively. By strengthening this skill set, the program can further empower student leaders to transform challenging situations into opportunities for growth and collaboration, aligning with the overarching goal of developing dynamic and adaptive leaders (Alviento, 2018; Gonzales, 2020).

Time Management Skill

Table 7 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison between the time management skills of the student leaders before and after the implementation of the student leadership training by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 7.
Comparison of the time management skills of the student leaders.

Conduct	N	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	t	p
Pre-Implementation	66	2.26	0.849	Low Level		
Post-Implementation	99	2.40	0.844	Low Level	-1.033	0.303

The comparison of time management skills, as presented in Table 7, before and after the training program indicated a slight increase in the mean score from 2.26 (± 0.849) to 2.40 (± 0.844). However, the t-value of -1.033 ($p=0.303$) shows that this difference is not statistically significant. While the results demonstrate a positive trend in the participant's ability to manage their time effectively, the absence of a significant change suggests that the program's impact on this particular skill was limited.

This outcome suggests an opportunity to enhance the training program by integrating more targeted interventions to develop time management competencies. Effective time management is crucial for balancing the responsibilities of student leadership roles and ensuring organizational goals are met (Gonzales, 2020). The program can help participants develop the discipline and strategies required for efficient time use by incorporating structured exercises, such as task prioritization workshops or simulated project timelines. Aligning these efforts with transformational principles, such as inspiring self-management and fostering accountability, could lead to more impactful and enduring improvements in this essential leadership skill (Nyaga, 2018; Schweisfurth et al., 2018).

Delegation Skill

Table 8 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison between delegation skills of the student leaders before and after the implementation of the student leadership training by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 8.
Comparison of the delegation skills of the student leaders.

Conduct	N	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	t	p
Pre-Implementation	66	2.16	0.892	Low Level	-0.701	0.484
Post-Implementation	99	2.27	0.997	Low Level		

The comparison of delegation skills, as presented in Table 8, before and after the training program revealed a slight increase in the mean score from 2.16 (± 0.892) to 2.27 (± 0.997). However, the t-value of -0.701 ($p=0.484$) indicates that the observed difference is not statistically significant. These findings suggest that while there was some improvement in the participants' ability to delegate tasks effectively, the change was not substantial enough to attribute directly to the training program.

Delegation is a critical leadership skill that ensures effective task distribution and fosters team collaboration. The lack of a significant improvement highlights the need for more focused training components that emphasize the practical application of delegation strategies (Alviento, 2018; Beltran, 2019a). Activities such as role-playing scenarios, group simulations, or case studies could provide participants hands-on experience in assigning tasks and empowering their team members (Kilag et al., 2023). By fostering a transformational approach that encourages trust and collaboration, the program could better prepare student leaders to delegate responsibilities confidently and effectively, ensuring the success of their organizations and the development of their team members' potential (Beltran, 2019b; Nyaga, 2018).

Motivation and Inspiration Skill

Table 9 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison between motivation and inspiration skills of the student leaders before and after the implementation of the student leadership training by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 9.
Comparison of the motivation and inspiration skills of the student leaders.

Conduct	N	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	t	p
Pre-Implementation	66	1.97	0.892	Low Level	-1.653	0.101
Post-Implementation	99	2.24	1.108	Low Level		

The comparison of motivation and inspiration skills, as presented in Table 9, before and after the leadership training program showed an increase in the mean score from 1.97 (± 0.892) to 2.24 (± 1.108), with a t-value of -1.653 ($p=0.101$). While this indicates an upward trend in participants' ability to inspire and motivate others, the statistical analysis shows insignificant improvement. This suggests that while some development occurred, it might not have been substantial or consistent across the participants to be conclusive.

Motivation and inspiration are vital components of effective leadership, as they drive individuals and teams toward achieving shared goals (Schweisfurth et al., 2018). The findings imply that while the training program addressed these aspects, it may benefit from incorporating more targeted interventions, such as interactive workshops or mentorship activities, to strengthen participants' skills in this area (Alviento, 2018; Kilag et al., 2023). By aligning with the principles

of fostering individualized support and inspirational motivation, the program could better equip student leaders to instill a sense of purpose and enthusiasm in their peers (Aguiling & Racelis, 2021). This refinement could lead to more impactful leadership practices, ensuring student organizations thrive through empowered and motivated teams.

Public Speaking Skill

Table 10 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison between public speaking skills of the student leaders before and after the implementation of the student leadership training by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 10.
Comparison of the public speaking skills of the student leaders.

Conduct	N	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	t	p
Pre-Implementation	66	2.44	0.806	Low Level	-1.021	0.309
Post-Implementation	99	2.56	0.738	Low Level		

The comparison of public speaking skills, as presented in Table 10, before and after the leadership training program revealed a slight increase in the mean score from 2.44 (± 0.806) to 2.56 (± 0.738), with a t-value of -1.021 ($p=0.309$). While this suggests an upward trend in participants' ability to speak in public settings effectively, the improvement was not statistically significant. This result implies that the program may have had a limited immediate impact on enhancing public speaking skills or that more time and practice are required to develop and internalize these skills fully.

Public speaking is a critical aspect of leadership, as it directly influences a leader's ability to inspire, motivate, and communicate effectively with their peers and teams (Nyaga, 2018). The findings indicate that while the training program introduced foundational strategies to improve public speaking, additional methods such as immersive speaking engagements, personalized feedback, and practice opportunities may be needed to achieve more significant outcomes (Mugot & Sumbalan, 2019; Gonzales, 2020). By emphasizing these elements, the program could foster leaders capable of confidently delivering speeches, presenting ideas, and addressing audiences—key attributes that resonate with transformational leadership principles and strengthen organizational dynamics (Schweisfurth et al., 2018).

Budgeting and Resource Management Skill

Table 11 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison between budgeting and resource management skills of the student leaders before and after the implementation of the student leadership training by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 11.
Comparison of the budgeting and resource management skills of the student leaders.

Conduct	N	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	t	p
Pre-Implementation	66	2.22	0.894	Low Level	-1.658	0.100
Post-Implementation	99	2.47	1.005	Low Level		

The comparison of budgeting and resource management skills, as presented in Table 11, before and after the leadership training program showed an increase in the mean score from 2.22 (± 0.894) to 2.47 (± 1.005), with a t-value of -1.658 ($p=0.100$). While the improvement indicates progress in students' understanding and applying these skills, the result was not statistically significant. This suggests that although the training provided exposure to effective strategies for managing resources and finances, its immediate impact on these skills may not have been sufficient to produce measurable gains within the study's timeframe.

Budgeting and resource management are fundamental to leadership roles, as they involve allocating limited resources efficiently to achieve organizational goals (Nyaga, 2018). The results highlight the importance of incorporating hands-on activities, such as simulated budget planning and resource allocation exercises, to enhance learning outcomes. Integrating such practical experiences within the program better aligns with the principles of transformational leadership by empowering student leaders to think critically, plan effectively, and make informed decisions. These improvements would strengthen individual competencies and foster a culture of responsibility and strategic foresight among emerging leaders (Schweisfurth et al., 2018; Vicente et al., 2023).

Strategic Planning Skill

Table 12 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison between strategic planning management skills of the student leaders before and after the implementation of the student leadership training by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 12.
Comparison of the strategic planning skills of the student leaders.

Conduct	N	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	t	p
Pre-Implementation	66	2.21	0.880	Low Level	-1.232	0.220
Post-Implementation	99	2.39	0.951	Low Level		

The comparison of strategic planning skills, as presented in Table 12, before and after the leadership training program showed an increase in the mean score from 2.21 (± 0.880) to 2.39 (± 0.951), with a t-value of -1.232 ($p=0.220$). While this indicates a positive shift in the participants' strategic planning capabilities, the improvement was insignificant. The modest increase suggests that the program introduced foundational elements of strategic thinking, such as goal-setting and prioritization. However, these may not have been sufficiently reinforced to yield substantial gains within the study's timeframe.

Strategic planning is a critical leadership skill that requires envisioning long-term goals and devising actionable steps to achieve them. The findings imply a need to strengthen program components that foster forward-thinking and decision-making skills (Nyaga, 2018; Kilag et al., 2024). Scenario planning, group strategy sessions, and real-life project simulations could better engage student leaders and deepen their understanding of strategic processes (Kilag et al., 2023). Aligning these elements with the program's objectives would support the transformative development of leadership by equipping participants to approach complex challenges with clarity and purpose, eventually enhancing their capacity to lead effectively in diverse contexts (Aguilung & Racelis, 2021).

Student Leadership Skills

Pre-implementation of the student leadership training program

Table 13 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison of the baseline results of individual student leadership skills prior to the implementation of the training program by the Office of Student Affairs.

Table 13.
Comparison of the baseline results of individual student leadership skills prior to the implementation of the training program.

Variables	\bar{x}	σ_x	F	p
Public Speaking	2.44 a	0.806	0.766	0.648
Communication	2.32 a	0.812		
Time Management	2.26 a	0.849		
Budgeting and Resource Management	2.22 a	0.894		
Strategic Planning	2.21 a	0.880		
Problem-Solving and Decision-Making	2.20 a	0.832		
Conflict Resolution	2.16 a	0.814		
Delegation	2.16 a	0.892		
Teamwork and Collaboration	2.07 a	0.912		
Motivation and Inspiration	1.97 a	0.892		

The ANOVA test results, as presented in Table 13, indicated no significant differences among the baseline means of individual student leadership skills prior to the implementation of the training program (F=0.766, p=0.648). The mean scores for the various skills showed minimal variation, with public speaking scoring the highest at 2.44 and motivation and inspiration scoring the lowest at 1.97. These findings suggest that the student leaders entered the program with relatively uniform proficiency levels across the evaluated skills, though some areas demonstrated slight disparities. This uniformity provides a consistent starting point for assessing the program's impact on developing these skills.

Post-implementation of the student leadership training program.

Table 14 presented the mean score, standard deviation, and the comparison of the post-training results of individual student leadership skills following the implementation of the program by the Office of Student Affairs.

The ANOVA test results, as presented in Table 14, for the post-training evaluation revealed significant differences in the individual leadership skills following the implementation of the training program (F=2.226, p=0.019). The mean scores across the evaluated skills demonstrated overall improvement, with public speaking achieving the highest mean of 2.56, followed closely by communication (2.48) and budgeting and resource management (2.47). Motivation and inspiration, while improved, remained the lowest-scoring skill, with a mean of 2.24. These results suggest that the training program effectively enhanced the students' leadership competencies, with specific skills exhibiting more pronounced development than others. The variation in post-training scores reflects the differential impact of the program on distinct aspects of leadership.

Table 14.

Comparison of the post-training results of individual student leadership skills following the implementation of the program.

Variables	\bar{x}	σ_x	F	<i>p</i>
Public Speaking	2.56 a	0.738		
Communication	2.48 ab	0.854		
Budgeting and Resource Management	2.47 ab	1.005		
Time Management	2.40 ab	0.844		
Strategic Planning	2.39 ab	0.951	2.226	0.019
Problem-Solving and Decision-Making	2.36 ab	0.954		
Conflict Resolution	2.32 ab	0.936		
Teamwork and Collaboration	2.30 ab	1.136		
Delegation	2.27 ab	0.997		
Motivation and Inspiration	2.24 b	1.108		

Note: $p < 0.05$

These findings underscore the capacity of the training program to cultivate diverse leadership skills, fostering a transformative shift in participants' capabilities (Nyaga, 2018; Schweisfurth et al., 2018; Dedicatoria et al., 2023). The significant differences indicate that the program successfully addressed skill-specific developmental needs, particularly in high-priority areas like public speaking and communication (Mugot & Sumbalan, 2019; Gonzales, 2020; Rogayan et al., 2021; Kilag et al., 2023; Fernando & Bual, 2024). Additionally, the result suggests that the program empowered students to inspire and engage their peers effectively, critical components of impactful leadership (Aguiling & Racelis, 2021; Bautista & Lim, 2021; Sarong, 2024). However, the relatively modest improvement in motivation and inspiration highlights the need for targeted strategies to amplify intrinsic motivation and the ability to inspire others (Amit, 2019; Beltran, 2019b; Friaes, 2021; Loyola, 2022). This insight can inform future iterations of the program, ensuring a balanced approach that maximizes its transformative potential and equips student leaders with the tools to drive meaningful change in their communities (Castro et al., 2020).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The study evaluated the result of a leadership training program on developing essential leadership skills among student leaders. The findings revealed measurable improvements in various competencies, including public speaking, communication, and budgeting, though the degree of enhancement varied across skills. Skills like public speaking consistently demonstrated higher post-training development, suggesting these areas were exceptionally responsive to the program's design. However, some skills, such as motivation and inspiration, showed more subtle advancements, highlighting specific areas that could benefit from further refinement and targeted interventions.

Overall, the training program successfully enhanced participants' leadership capabilities, as evidenced by significant differences in skill levels following its implementation. The results emphasized the program's ability to address diverse leadership competencies while revealing the need for additional focus on underdeveloped areas. These findings suggest that the program is an effective platform for student leadership development, fostering skills that enable students to manage responsibilities, inspire others, and contribute meaningfully to their communities.

The study concludes that the leadership training program positively influenced the development of essential leadership skills, fostering growth in critical areas such as communication and strategic planning. While the program successfully enhanced overall competencies, the varying degrees of skill improvement highlight opportunities for further optimization. Future program iterations can provide a more comprehensive and balanced approach by incorporating targeted strategies to address areas with modest advancements, such as motivation and inspiration. These findings affirm the program's transformative potential, contributing to the holistic development of student leaders and equipping them with the tools necessary for effective and impactful leadership.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To enhance public *speaking skills*, the Office of Student Affairs and Services could integrate regular practice opportunities, such as speech competitions, debate forums, or presentations, into the leadership training program. This would help participants build confidence and improve their articulation in public settings. For *communication skills*, interactive workshops focusing on active listening, nonverbal communication, and persuasive speaking could be implemented. Role-playing exercises simulating real-world scenarios allow participants to practice and refine their interpersonal communication.

To strengthen *time management skills*, the program could incorporate sessions on prioritization techniques, such as the Eisenhower Matrix, and provide tools for creating effective schedules. Follow-up activities could track participants' ability to balance academic, personal, and leadership responsibilities. For *budgeting and resource management skills*, hands-on training involving case studies or mock financial planning exercises could be introduced. Participants could work on managing resources for hypothetical events to develop practical decision-making abilities in financial contexts. In enhancing *strategic planning skills*, scenario-based planning exercises and group projects that require setting long-term goals and creating action plans could be emphasized. Collaboration with professionals in strategic roles also offers valuable insights. To improve *problem-solving and decision-making skills*, the program could include sessions on critical thinking and structured problem-solving frameworks, such as SWOT analysis. Real-life problem-solving simulations could further help participants develop adaptive thinking under pressure.

For *conflict resolution skills*, the training could feature workshops on mediation techniques and emotional intelligence. Simulations of conflict scenarios could provide a safe environment for participants to practice resolving disputes effectively. To advance *delegation skills*, the program could focus on teaching participants how to identify team members' strengths and assign tasks accordingly. Team-based projects with designated leaders could allow participants to practice delegating responsibilities. For *teamwork and collaboration skills*, activities such as team-building exercises, cooperative games, and group challenges could help participants strengthen their ability to work harmoniously with others toward a shared goal. Finally, to foster *motivation and inspiration skills*, the program could include leadership case studies showcasing transformational leaders and their motivational approaches. Participants could also practice creating and delivering motivational speeches to inspire peers.

To address the overall low-level outcomes of the leadership training program, the Office of Student Affairs and Services could consider a comprehensive redesign of the program's structure,

content, and delivery methods. Emphasizing experiential learning, the program could integrate immersive activities such as leadership retreats, mentorship opportunities, and community service projects to reinforce the practical application of skills. Additionally, the program should adopt a more personalized approach by conducting initial assessments of participants' existing competencies and tailoring the training to their needs and skill gaps. Continuous feedback mechanisms, such as periodic evaluations and reflective sessions, could also be implemented to monitor progress and adapt the program dynamically. A more intensive focus on advanced leadership theories, combined with practical workshops and real-world scenarios, would likely result in a significant and measurable improvement in student leaders' competencies.

FURTHER STUDIES

Future research could explore the long-term impacts of leadership training programs by tracking participants' skill application and growth in real-world settings over time. Comparative studies could also evaluate the efficacy of different training methodologies, such as immersive simulations versus traditional workshops, to determine the most effective formats for developing specific leadership competencies. Additionally, examining the influence of demographic and contextual factors, such as organizational environment, on leadership skill development could provide insights into how training programs can be customized to meet diverse student populations' unique needs.

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